

Bidimensional Reinforcement of a Polyester Resin by Jute and Glass Fibers

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ABSTRACT

A study was made of the use of jute and glass fibers as bidimensional reinforcement of an unsaturated polyester resin matrix. Composites were fabricated with jute and glass fibers, separately as well as in the hybrid form. The latter had always glass fibers in the outer layers. The bidimensional jute fibers were used in two forms: (i) in the form of fabrics and (ii) in the form of untwisted fibers at 0° and 90° with respect to the composite major axis. The modulus and strength of composites were analyzed as functions of fiber volume fractions. Fracture surfaces were examined in SEM to study the failure modes in these composites.

The jute fabric composites showed a higher Young's modulus but lower fracture stress than the matrix. However, the composites containing untwisted jute fibers bidimensionally arranged showed effective reinforcement in both modulus and strength. The explanation for this different behavior is that the process of making jute fabric results in an accentuated twist in the fibers, besides fiber breakage and degradation.

The hybrid composites, with jute fibers substituting part of glass fibers, showed much better reinforcement, indicating thereby a great promise in substituting expensive glass fibers by cheap jute fibers.

INTRODUCTION

Fibers obtained from vegetable kingdom (e.g., jute, sisal, ramie etc.) have traditionally been used for making cords and sacks. Brazil is a major producer of these fibers. In an on-going research program, since 1975, we have studied the structure and mechanical properties of these fibers and their use as a resin reinforcing fiber, either alone or in conjunction with glass fiber (1-4). Independent work of a similar nature has been done at other institutions (5-7). The viability of substitution, partial or total, of glass fibers by jute fibers in unidirectional reinforcement was demonstrated in an earlier work (4). The objective of this work was to evaluate this substitution in bidimensional reinforcement.

EXPERIMENTAL

Composites were made by incorporating jute fibers in the form of a fabric

or as unidirectional fibers at 0° and 90° and glass fibers in the form of a fabric in an unsaturated polyester resin by leaky mold technique. In hybrid composites, a ratio of $V_f = 2 V_g$ was maintained, where V_j and V_g are jute and glass fiber volume fractions, respectively. Specimens cut out from composites sheets were tested in tension and in flexure. The tensile tests were conducted in an Instron machine (100 kN capacity) with an Instron clip-on gage for measuring the deformation.

The fiber volume fractions were measured by optical microscopy using the point counting method. A scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM-U3), operating at between 10-15 kV in secondary mode, was used to study the fracture surfaces. The fracture surfaces were sputter-coated with gold to minimize the charging.

RESULTS

Both Jute and Glass in Fabric Form

The variation of Young's modulus, E , and maximum tensile strength, σ , with jute fiber (in fabric form) volume fraction, V_f , is shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. One notes that the Young's modulus increases with V_f and there is a definite improvement over that of resin. The same, however, cannot be said of strength which is, in fact, less than that of resin and more or less independent of V_f . In the case of glass fiber (fabric), as expected, both σ and E increased linearly with V_g . In the case of hybrid composites with both glass and jute in the fabric form ($V_j = 2 V_g$) the variation of these parameters is shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

In the case of jute composites, the fracture occurred along the transverse fibers. Figure 5 a shows a fracture surface wherein one sees the 90° jute fibers. The aspect of these jute fibers (notice the twisted fibers) indicates that jute/resin interface is weak. In glass fiber composites and hybrid composites the fracture consisted of a mixture of transverse as well as inter-laminar modes. In the hybrid composites also the transverse fracture mode was associated with the presence of 90° jute fibers. Similar fracture behavior was observed in flexure with these composites.

Unidirectional Jute Fibers Placed at 0° and 90° and Glass Fabric

The variation of Young's modulus, E , and fracture stress, σ , with fiber volume fraction is shown in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively, indicating a linear dependence of these parameters on fiber volume fraction. Similar variation of σ and E with V_f was observed for hybrid composites.

The fracture behavior of these jute composites and that of the hybrid composites was similar to that of jute composites made from jute fabric.

DISCUSSION

The jute fiber composites show a better mechanical performance when they are unidirectionally aligned at 0° and 90° rather than when they are used in the fabric form. In the latter case, these fibers are twisted and suffer a degradation in their strength due to this twist in the fibers and possibly due to handling. Figure 8 shows jute and glass fabrics. Notice the twisted and broken jute fibers while the glass fibers are almost straight, unbroken fibers. In these twisted jute fibers, the stress distribution will be different from that in an untwisted yarn of fibers. Krenchel (8) has shown that the smaller the pitch of helix, the smaller will be the reinforcement efficiency.

Thus, the poor performance of composites containing jute fibers in the fabric form is mainly attributable to the process of fabricating jute yarn which involves twisting of these jute fibers. The twisting of fibers during yarn spinning makes only a portion of fiber strength available reinforcement. Weaker jute/resin interface compared to glass/resin interface may also have contributed to the poor performance.

As this work was finished, we came to know of a work (9) carried out at the Fibre Research Institute, TND, The Netherlands on twistless spinning of jute

fibers, confirming thereby the adverse effect of twist in jute fibers introduced during spinning.

CONCLUSIONS

Jute fabric composites showed improvement over the resin in Young's modulus but not in strength. The reason for this was that in manufacturing of jute yarn, the fibers are twisted and damaged. Thus, jute fibers contribute only a portion of their potential toward reinforcement. In jute/glass (fabric) hybrid composites there occurred an improvement in both strength and modulus. Apparently, the positive contribution of glass fabric masked the negative contribution of jute fabric.

Composites made from unidirectional (i.e. untwisted) jute fibers aligned at 0° and 90° to obtain a bidimensional reinforcement showed effective reinforcement in both modulus and strength. This confirmed the adverse effect of twist in jute fabrics. Hybrid composites consisting of glass fiber fabrics and straight jute fibers aligned at 0° and 90° showed even better results indicating the great promise they hold.

It is suggested that a process of making a twistless jute fabric will go a long way toward improving the performance of these composites.

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Fig. 1 - Variation of Young's modulus, E , with jute fiber volume fraction, V_f (in fabric form).

Fig. 2 - Variation of ultimate tensile strength, σ , with jute fiber volume fraction, V_f (in fabric form). Notice the lack of reinforcement.

Fig. 3 - Variation of Young's modulus, E , with hybrid fiber volume fraction, V_f . Both glass and jute were in the fabric form. (cf. Fig.1).

Fig. 4 - Variation of ultimate tensile strength, σ , with hybrid fiber volume fraction, V_f . Both glass and jute were in the fabric form, with $V_j = 2 V_g$. (cf. Fig.2).

Fig. 5 - Fracture surface of a jute (fabric) composites. Notice the twisted jute fibers at 90° to the stress axis.

Fig. 6 - Variation of Young's modulus, E , with jute fiber volume fraction, V_f . Unidirectional (untwisted) jute fibers placed at 0° and 90° . cf. Fig.1.

Fig. 7 - Variation of ultimate tensile strength, σ , with jute fiber volume fraction, V_f . Unidirectional (untwisted) jute fibers placed at 0° and 90° . Notice the distinct strength reinforcement. cf. Fig.2.

Fig. 8 - (a) jute fabric showing twisted jute fibers.
 (b) glass fabric showing twistless glass fibers.

